

DEVELOPMENT OF INFUSION STRATEGY FOR COMPOSITE RAILROAD HOPPER CAR WITH FLOW SIMULATION AND VALIDATION

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ABSTRACT

In 2012 the Russian scientific and production enterprise of “Applied Advanced Technologies” (ApATeCh), in cooperation with Lightweight Structures B.V. started to work on the development of a composite roof and body of a railroad freight train or hopper car. The advantage of composites in this traditionally steel application would be the reduced weight and better durability when corrosive goods like fertiliser are transported. The challenging objective was to have the complete composite hopper car roof and hopper car body (see Figure 1), including all structural components such as frames and stiffeners, produced in one shot, with no need for subsequent assembly.

Manufacturing of composite structures by the vacuum infusion process has its own advantages, but it requires a detailed understanding of the resin infusion process. To enable fabrication of the car body as an integrated monolithic structure without manufacturing defects, advanced resin flow simulations were used in combination with simple small-scale laboratory infusion tests to calibrate the models. In this way, it was possible to produce first-time-right parts, without the need for a lot of expensive experiments, which are normally needed for development of the final configuration of infusion process. This approach of process modelling and simulation in combination with practical validation experiments has been applied successfully for other large composite structures before [[3]]. Impregnation process modeling was conducted with PAM-RTM software [1].

Figure 1: One-third section of the hopper car roof (left) and hopper car body (right)

The representative sections that seemed to have the greatest risk of occurrence of dry and un-impregnated zones based on a global infusion simulation (indicated in Figure 1 in red ellipses) were used to develop detailed flow simulation models. Glass-fibre permeability was measured by special in-house developed in-plane and through-thickness permeameters [[2]].

Comparison of results of impregnation modeling of one-third roof section with the results of practical infusion experiment showed excellent correlation, both for the flow front progression and the impregnation time. From those preliminary results, impregnation process strategies were developed for the complete hopper car roof and body. These were both impregnated in one shot on the first try without any serious defects. The parts were trimmed, roof and body were assembled, painted and mounted on an existing steel under-structure into the first complete composite hopper car (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Complete hopper car

1. INTRODUCTION

Vacuum infusion is a composite manufacturing process, where liquid resin is drawn in a dry fibre lay-up by means of vacuum. Numerical modelling of this vacuum infusion process makes it possible to conduct virtual manufacturing experiments, thus saving time and money necessary to find an optimum infusion strategy. Present article describes an experimental study on numerical modelling of impregnation process of vacuum infusion of large composite structures of hopper car roof and body.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF INFUSION STRATEGY FOR ROOF STRUCTURE

To optimize the impregnation process for the whole composite hopper roof structure, smaller sample components were manufactured at first, structurally similar to the areas of frames, catwalks, reinforcing beam (see Figure 1 (left)), etc. Then models of sample parts impregnation process were developed within PAM-RTM environment and model parameters, i.e. viscosity, permeability, vacuum conditions, were adjusted. The values of reinforcement permeability were obtained experimentally with the use of in-plane and through-thickness permeameters at APATECH production facility (see Figure 3) [[2]].

Figure 3: Measurement of in-plane and through-thickness permeability characteristics of dry fibre reinforcements

A sample part representing skin/reinforcing beam transition area was used to adjust numerical model implemented in PAM-RTM in terms of vacuum conditions (pump pressure, valve open/close timings), see Figure 4. Experimentally measured impregnation time for the sample part constituted 85 minutes compared to 84.5 minutes predicted in PAM-RTM software. This good correlation gave confidence for the execution of the production of a one-third section of the roof.

Figure 4: Experimental tests and adjustment of impregnation model based on representative sample part (skin/reinforcing beam transition area)

Impregnation results obtained during fabrication of one-third section of the roof structure were used to calibrate the flow simulation. The simulation has been conducted using the mathematical model developed by TsAGI specialists in PAM-RTM environment, based on data collected during the first stage of the study. Flow front progression and impregnation time simulation results were found to be in a good agreement with experimental data. PAM-RTM simulated impregnation time constituted 95 minutes compared to 92 minutes obtained during the experiment. It should be noted that one-third section of the roof sample structure included over 10 different lay-ups with thicknesses of 2 to 16 mm and complex areas of stiffeners transition (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Modelling of one-third roof structure

Modelling of full scale roof structure in PAM-RTM environment was made before actual infusion of roof structure. Modelling the impregnation process with proposed "herringbone" configuration has

revealed the possible location of poorly impregnated areas within reinforcing beam and frames. The observations have confirmed the formation of air bubbles in those areas during actual impregnation (see Figure 6), however, the additional evacuation made it possible to eliminate these defects and to fully impregnate the roof structure.

Figure 6: Defects predicted for the applied vacuum configuration (left) and confirmed during actual impregnation; the impregnation of full-size hopper roof structure (right)

3. DEVELOPMENT OF INFUSION STRATEGY FOR HOPPER CAR BODY STRUCTURE

Injection system configuration for the hopper car body impregnation has been developed at the next stage of the study (see Figure 8). The goal was to find such a configuration of the injection system that would prevent the formation of un-impregnated areas and that the impregnation time would not exceed the pot life of the matrix (150 minutes). Several configurations of the injection system were optimized for 3 configurations of FE mesh, i.e. «1/4», «1/3» and simplified version of full car body. Hopper body structure included 13 types of composite lay-up (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: FE models for impregnation process simulation (left) and areas of different reinforcement lay-ups (right)

Two principal configurations of the injection system have been considered at first (see Figure 8). The first one is a linear 3-level injection system with a sequential activation of each level and with the distance between levels of 1 m; second one is a tree-like injection system.

Figure 8: Principal configurations of injection system

Following conclusions may be made considering both configurations:

- Configuration 1 ensures more uniform flow front distribution within body structure preform with no need of additional vacuum channels to be installed at the central frame provided the pot life of matrix system is over 4 hours;
- Configuration 2 allows 3 times faster impregnation but requires an installation of additional vacuum channels at the central frame (at the top and bottom of the frame);
- Non-uniform flow front distribution in Configuration 2 and multiple joining fronts may potentially lead to formation of air bubbles (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Car body impregnation time: Configuration 1 (left) and Configuration 2 (right)

Upon closer examination of simulation results process engineers have found sequential configuration of injection system to be rather complex for implementation and suggested further investigation of a tree-like configuration. Following adjustments have been made to the configuration:

- Extension of injection channels near the upper edge of the car body;
- Installation of additional channels at front / end walls;
- Optimization of injection channels position for uniform impregnation.

Changes in injection system configuration have allowed an impregnation time to be decreased from 4710 seconds (~ 118 minutes) to 3220 seconds (~ 54 minutes) (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Tree-like configuration of injection system (simplified model)

The injection system configuration very similar to that optimized in the course of this study was used in production of the hopper car. Several modifications were made including installation of additional vacuum channels near frames for uniform impregnation; extension of channels closer to the upper edge of a car body, and a number of other changes (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Hopper car body under vacuum bag

Injection system configuration adopted by process engineers enabled fabrication of fully impregnated hopper body structure on the first try well before the start of matrix gelation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The hopper car roof and body were both impregnated in one shot on the first try without any serious defects. The parts were trimmed, roof and body were assembled, painted and mounted on an existing steel under-structure into the first complete composite hopper car (see Figure 2). Based on results of the study several conclusions can be made:

- Preliminary simulation of vacuum infusion process allows optimization of dozens of configurations of injection system instead of only one.
- An accurate prediction will require knowledge of in-plane (K1, K2) and through-thickness (K3) permeability coefficients for all materials used in fabrication of structure including reinforcements, flow media etc.

ApATeCh became the winner of the JEC group Innovation Awards Europe 2014 programme with its composite hopper car body fabricated by vacuum infusion, for details see: <http://www.jecomposites.com/events/innovation-awards-europe-2014/innovation-program/2014-winners>.

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